

ASCENDANCY OF STORE IMAGE ON CUSTOMER BEHAVIOR: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT: The store is most important mode of communication between a retailer and its shoppers. Store is the place where all the sales happen or not to happen. Retailers should cater an enthusiastic and prosper shopping environment in the store to get the desired image, sales and profit from the targeted visitors. A good store image entices customers to make a purchase, spent more money and time, revisit, impulse purchase and also maintain customer interest, increase frequency to visit store. Store image has also an impact on store choice, store satisfaction, store loyalty, attitude towards store and perceived risk. Store image not only influence the customer perception, purchase intention, purchase making decisions, learning, life style, and benefits but also motivate them to spread positive word of mouth. The purpose of this paper was to analyze the influences of store image on customer behavior. Customers/visitors of shopping centers (n=200) were surveyed on random basis through printed questionnaires by face to face interview during November-December 2010. Weighted Average Score Method and Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample Test have been applied to test the hypothesis. A significant influence of store image has been found on customer behaviour. The study was confined to only selected region of Pune district (Maharashtra) with randomly selected customers/visitors of shopping centers. The study will prove to be a great help for researchers/management students who want to do similar or related study in the future.

Key words: Store Image, Customer Behaviour, Shopping Center, Retailing, Pune.

INTRODUCTION

The store has traditionally occupied a central role in retailing as the direct point of contact between retailer and consumer. It is the place where the retailer can meet customer's requirement and ensure continued business. The store is also an important extension of the retailer's image (Newman & Cullen 2002). A retailer uses the store to establish a competitive advantage and communicate its offering to the consumer. Defining store image is far from easy (eg Sewell 1974). James *et. al.* (1976) defined store image is as a set of attributes based upon evaluation of those stores attributes, deemed important by consumers. The interplay of these tangible and intangible elements and the customers overall interpretation of them, based upon previous knowledge and experiences, are widely accepted to determine store image (Hirschman 1981, Marzursky and Jacoby 1986).

The mixture of tangible and intangible dimensions and the complexity of meanings and relationships attributed to retailers by customers have long been recognized (eg Myers 1960, Arons 1961, Weale 1961, Rich and Portis 1964, Kunkel and Berry 1968, Perry and Norton 1970, May 1974, Marks 1976). Martineau (1958) is attributed with being one of the first to discuss "store personality", Lindquist (1974) develops the distinction between "functional qualities" and "psychological attributes", and Oxenfeld (1974) argues that store image is a concept which is "more than the sum of its parts...., it represents interaction among characteristics and includes extraneous elements..., it has some emotional content... a combination of factual and emotional material". Although originating from an attempt to explain retail identity in an advertising context, Kapferer's (1986) identity prism, comprising physical, personality, cultural, relational, reflection, and customer self interest facets, similarly combines functional and symbolic elements and stresses the importance of the customers de-coding of these facets. The store image may be created with the help of the exterior of the store, the internal layout of the store, methods of the display, atmospherics such as lighting, sounds, smells and colours (Kotler 1974). Before inhabiting on the hypothesis of the research, a brief review of literature has been covered.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mayer (1989) suggested that store image has been one of the main topics in retailing. Pan and Zinkhan (2006) in their study concluded that store image and attributes strongly affects the store visit frequency. Crating an image depends heavily on a retailer's atmosphere- which is comprised of all of its physical characteristics, such as the store exterior,

the general interior, layout, and display (Berman and Evans 2008). O'Casey and Grace (2008) explain that little effort has, however, been devoted to understanding the effects of consumer image-store image congruency. Image congruency has not only been shown to be valuable in relation to product choices, but has also been shown to contribute to our understanding of retail store choice and preferences. Their study examines the effect of retailer service provision and the retail store environment (servicescape) on the customers' perception of value for money. The study also examines the role of self-store image congruence in the above relationships. The findings confirm the hypothesized relationships in the conceptual model (except for servicescape effects). The findings also indicate that the effects are stronger for those individuals experiencing high self-store image congruence.

Newman & Cullion (2002) believed that the key to success in retailing is to create a store image that is congruent with the life styles and expectations of the consumers that the retailer is targeting. Retailers try to increase the number of impulse purchase through store design, product displays, package design and sales (Hoyer & MacInnis 1997). Sherman *et al.* (1997) who found a positive effect of arousal in a mallbased specialty store. Shopping for groceries is commonly conceived of as an end to be achieved in the most efficient manner. Few consumers find grocery shopping personally gratifying (Levy and Weitz 2001). Store image is critical component in store choice and store loyalty (eg. Arons 1961, Doyle and Fenwick 1974, Lewis and Hawksley 1990, Malhotra 1983, Nevin and Houston 1980, Osman 1993, Stanley and Sewall 1976).

By separating the stores according to average consumer perceptions of competitor attractiveness, Siroh *et. al.* (1998) studied out that perceived value does play an important role in the determination of store loyalty intention if there is a high degree of competitor attractiveness. When this attractiveness is low, results of the study fail to show relevance for perceived value for money. The appropriate ambience for luxury goods retail varies with the product category. For high-tech gadgets, a bright and vibrant atmosphere is suitable. The colour combination should be appropriate to the context and the customer should feel relaxed in the store. Well experienced professional interior designers are often engaged for creating a good retail environment for luxury products (Kumar 2009).

Kenhove *et. al.* (1999) revealed that the nature of the task executed by retailers influences consumers on their store choice decision. The study also indicates that larger quantities, immediacy of purchase, routine purchase have an impact on store choice decision. Sinha and Banerjee (2004) studied store choice behavior and their study attempts that proximity to residence and comfort level are major factors to visit outlets. Miranda and Konyal (2005) noted that overall satisfaction from store did not affect the customer loyalty. It is affected by several reasons such as- frequently buyer reward schemes, travel distance, preference for an in-store delicatessen, size of the average grocery bill, store signage and level of sale assistance.

A number of studies however point to the issues associated with implementing image and the dissonance which may exist between management and consumer perceptions of store image. Marcus (1972) examined image variation across stores within a chain, and Oppewal and Timmermans (1997) explored management perceptions of store image in a competitive context. Others, have compared management or corporate views of image with customer views, highlighting the "gap" in perceptions which often exists (McClure and Ryan 1968, Pathak *et. al.* 1974, Samli and Lincoln 1989, Keaveny and Hunt 1992) Given the even greater potential for misinterpretation of image arising from cultural and behavioural differences in international markets, one might expect these potential problems of dissonance to be amplified when entering a foreign market.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

On the basis of literature review and the objectives of the study, the following hypothesis has been formulated-

H₁- The store image has positive influences on customer behavior.

H₂- Degree of influence of store image differs to customers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY-

Our study was based on both primary and secondary data, secondary data played an important role to review of literature, formulate hypothesis, and questionnaire preparation. It was collected from books, journals, magazines, websites and some other published sources available and references for the same are given at the end of the paper. This research was conducted using a questionnaire to understand the influences of store image on consumer behavior. For the study a questionnaire containing 20 parameters of consumer behavior was constructed. The questionnaire consisted of Likert (1970) Scale (basically an ordinal scale) ranging from highly influenced (+2) to highly uninfluenced (-2) with the middle of scale identified by the response alternative neither influenced nor uninfluenced (0). A pilot study was carried out through a questionnaire containing both open and closed ended questions. Taking the insight from the preliminary survey, the questionnaire was modified for the final study. The questionnaire was administered personally using face to face method in order to improve responses for collecting primary data.

The validity of scales used in questionnaire was measured through face & content validity. Face validity is the extent to which a measurement scale seems to measure what is supposed to measure (McDaniel & Gates 2001). This was determined by the judgment of the researcher, who compiled the questionnaire with various scales, which logically appeared to accurately reflect what they were supposed to measure. Content validity was measured by firstly defining what exactly needed to be measure. In this study, key components were identified through the hypothesis constructed that helped to identified what needed to be measured. Second by doing extensive review of literature and conducting focused groups helped to identify all possible items were identified. Third, opinions were sought from experts on whether certain items should be included or even excluded. Statisticians were approached to access the scale and item selected for the study. The reliability of the scale was assessed through the adaption of the research of Copper & Schindler (2006). The internal consistency of reliability when items in the measurement scale coincided with the same underlying construct was measured by using Cronbach's Alfa. The Alfa value was 0.895 which can be said to be indicator of good reliability of the instruments.

The present study was conducted during 2010-11. The sample size for the study was 200, drawn randomly from the customers/visitors of shopping centers when they visited these centers on week days. The sample was selected from the Pune district of Maharashtra. The sample method was Random sampling of Probability Sample Technique.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The responses of respondents regarding demographic characteristics were taken on Nominal and ordinal scales. Simple percentage method has been used to analyze the demographic variables of respondents. The demographic characteristics of the respondents for this study are presented in Table 1.

Sr. No.	Variable	Sub-Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1)	Gender	Male	107	53.50
		Female	93	46.50
2)	Age (Years)	Below 21	08	04.00
		21 to 30	61	30.50
		31 to 40	53	26.50
		41 to 50	41	20.50
		Above 50	37	18.50
3)	Marital Status	Single	95	47.50
		Married	105	52.50
4)	Educational Status	Illiterate	05	02.50
		Below 10th	31	15.50
		10th to 12th	56	28.00
		Graduation	53	26.50
		Post Graduation	55	27.50
5)	Occupation Status	Student	32	16.00
		Salaried	52	26.00
		Self-Employed	28	14.00
		House Wife	63	31.50
		Other	25	12.50
6)	Household Income (Yearly) (₹)	< 1 Lakh	25	12.50
		1 - 2 Lakhs	61	30.50
		2 - 5 Lakhs	68	34.00
		> 5 Lakhs	46	23.00

Weighted average method was applied to test the hypothesis H_1 . The chart 1 depicts the Weighted Average Scores of the respondents regarding the different parameters of consumer behavior included in this study. These scores support the hypothesis H_1 . Therefore hypothesis H_1 is accepted.

To test the hypothesis H_2 , Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample test has been employed. It is similar to Chi Square Test, test of goodness of fit. Table 2 depicts calculated K-S 'D' values for each parameters of consumer behavior included in this study. The critical value of D at an alpha of 1% level of significance is 0.115. As the calculated D exceeds the critical value of 0.115, the hypothesis H_2 is accepted.

Table 2: Statistics of Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) 'D' Values for each Parameter		
Sr. No.	Parameters	K-S 'D' Value*
1.	Purchase Making Decisions	0.220

2.	Purchase Intention	0.260
3.	Make a Purchase	0.245
4.	Impulse Purchase	0.320
5.	Frequency to Visit	0.275
6.	Time Spend in Store	0.295
7.	Money Spending	0.275
8.	Maintain Customer Interest	0.320
9.	Store Choice	0.295
10.	Store Satisfaction	0.320
11.	Store Revisit	0.300
12.	Store Loyalty	0.290
13.	Perceived Risk	0.255
14.	Positive Word of Mouth	0.315
15.	Life Style	0.315
16.	Attitude	0.280
17.	Benefits	0.285
18.	Leanings	0.307
19.	Perception	0.305
20.	Motivation	0.310

* K-S 'D' Values are based on responses of respondents and calculated from the appendix 1.

CONCLUSION

Most of the customers/visitors of shopping centers are youth, highly educated, having good household income. The result of the study shows that store image has positive influence on customer behavior. Result also depicts a high degree of influence of store image on customer behavior. As we heard again and again that as a retailer you never get a second chance to make a first impression. So it is important to create a good store image. A good store image entices customers to make a purchase, spend more money and time, revisit, impulse purchase and also maintain customer interest, increase frequency to visit store. Store image has also impact on store choice, store satisfaction, store loyalty, attitude towards store, and perceived risk. Store image not only influence the customer perception, purchase intention, purchase making decisions, learning, life style, and benefits but also motivate customers to spread positive word of mouth.

To create a good store image, we have to remember that the most visible element of the store is the design of its storefront or exterior and interior décor (Dunne *et. al.* 2007). The storefront or exterior must be eye catching, inviting, and reflective of the merchandise offered inside. The interior décor must be comfortable, put the shoppers in the proper buying mood, and provide a backdrop that enhances but does not over-power merchandise so that as a retailer we can cater an enthusiastic and prosper shopping environment to get the desired sales and profit from the targeted segments.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS & IMPLICATIONS

This study was limited to customers/visitors of shopping centers selected on random basis. For want of time and resources study was confined to only selected regions. Frauds/fault in giving the right information may not be neglected. This study furnishes information about various demographic characteristics of customers. The study helps

the responsible management of shopping centers to create more effective and attractive store image to attract new customers and to retain existing customers. The study will further prove to be a great help to the researchers/management students who want to do similar or related study in the future.

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Appendix 1. Responses of Respondents for each Parameter						
Sr. No.	Parameters	Highly Influenced	Influenced	Neither influenced nor uninfluenced	Uninfluenced	Highly Uninfluenced
1.	Purchase Making Decisions	39	66	59	34	02
2.	Purchase Intention	38	71	63	25	03
3.	Make a Purchase	27	78	64	30	01
4.	Impulse Purchase	39	81	64	12	04
5.	Frequency to Visit	28	79	68	24	01
6.	Time Spend in Store	44	67	68	14	07
7.	Money Spending	26	79	70	22	03
8.	Maintain Customer Interest	35	70	79	13	03
9.	Store Choice	51	72	56	16	05
10.	Store Satisfaction	37	77	70	12	04
11.	Store Revisit	42	73	65	12	08
12.	Store Loyalty	25	80	73	17	05
13.	Perceived Risk	39	63	69	26	03
14.	Positive Word of Mouth	36	78	69	14	03
15.	Life Style	33	70	80	14	03
16.	Attitude	41	70	65	18	06
17.	Benefits	40	69	68	12	11
18.	Leanings	31	76	74	12	07
19.	Perception	29	77	75	15	04
20.	Motivation	32	72	78	14	04